

Enhancing Student Academic Performance: Application Of Concept Mapping

Obaid Ullah, Abdul Waheed Mughal, Saira Nudrat

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 03, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: February 27, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Concept Mapping, Academic Achievements, Undergraduate Students</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4568356</p>	<p><i>Concept mapping is a teaching strategy that teachers employ for facilitating students in their academics and learning. This study aims to explore the role and impact of concept mapping on students' academic development. Using a quantitative research design, the sample of the study consisted of 108 students selected through sample size determination techniques. The data was collected, through a validated closed questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale, from the respondents through proportionate sampling techniques and was analyzed by Friedman test using SPSS v.20. The results revealed that concept mapping fails to assist in recalling a wide range of materials in a systematic way; it does not assist in coping with the main course content and it lacks the support of various linking concepts between segments of topics. The study recommends that training on a regular basis should be provided to teachers and wide-ranging applicability of concept mapping as a teaching style needs to form part of classroom teaching.</i></p>

Introduction

Learning is a complex and systematic process (Adey & Shayer, 1994), involving interplay between and interaction of cognitive, affective, and psychomotor domains (Baron & Byrne, 2003; Huffman, 2004; Joyce, Weil & Calhoun, 2004). Over the years, with their roots in relevant educational theories, several teaching strategies have evolved, which propound active student-centered participation; yet, in Pakistan, it is well documented that teaching strategies are teacher dominant and students are involved in passive learning (Iqbal, 2011). However, it is well established empirically, that the curriculum should be focused on developing concepts and critical thinking approaches among students. In other words, concept development should underpin the curriculum process, which results in clarifying basic concepts leading to other concepts and so on. Thus, an academic journey is processed from developing concepts from easy to complex; where the prior concepts act as a base for the next one and helps in developing relationship among the given concepts (Ke, 2013).

Concept mapping is a technique through which information are provided for developing linkage between the concepts and their relationship. Research studies indicated that concept mapping can be opted as a best option for teaching because it yields desired outcomes in each time frame (Canas, Novak & Reiska, 2012). Research studies also recommend concept mapping as a teaching strategy from primary to university level as it provides an opportunity to students in conceptualizing the complex academic contents. In fact, concept mapping is employed in measuring the achievement of learning objectives, students' academic assessments, and planning and for clarifying misconceptions in certain academic content in the longer benefit of students (Nesbit & Adesope, 2006; Novak & Cañas, 2006a, 2006b). Research indicates that the content, which is taught to students through concept mapping has long lasting effects on the memory of students and the students have strong conceptual understanding (Hilbert & Renkl, 2007; O'Donnell, Dansereau & Hall, 2002). Besides this, the students are motivated to learn through concept mapping (Mintzes, Wandersee, & Novak, 2000), because this strategy provides a base for developing connection between the terminologies and vocabulary with each other. In fact, this strategy is applicable in all fields of science and education. According to Hay, Kinchin, and Lygo-Baker (2008) concept mapping is often used in science subjects where the focus is initially on a topic or content; from which difficult terminologies or vocabulary are taken and listed in systematic order. Next to that, these terminologies or vocabularies are linked with each other to generate meaningful information, which are presented in the form of graphical representation.

Most researches have focused on pattern of development of concept mapping in an academic setting. Concept maps are often designed in the form of a sequential hierarchy, which provides a quick overview of the concept in hand (Cañas, Valerio, Lalinde-Pulido, Carvalho, & Arguedas, 2003; Coffey, Reichherzer, Owsnick-Klewe, & Wilde, 2012; Ke, 2013; Chen & Bai, 2010; Chen & Sue, 2013; Qasim, Jeong, Heu, & Lee, 2013; Valerio Arbizu,

2014). The process of developing concept mapping includes the placement of labelled concepts in various shapes i.e. may be in circle or square or triangle or rectangular; linking basic or relevant terminologies or vocabulary thus connecting in an order to yield proper concept (Åhlberg&Ahoranta, 2004). According to Luksa (2011), students can learn through concept mapping where they are involved in making connections of the missing links and concepts using diagrams. This strategy makes the contents interesting to students and they develop focus towards their learning (Henige, 2012). It is also evident from research findings that concept mapping is also considered as an effective instrument for teaching-learning process (Ben Salem, ChenitiBelcadhi, & Braham, 2013; Jetter&Kok, 2014; Kibar, Yaman, & Ayas, 2013; Kumaran&Sankar, 2013; Watson, Pelkey, Noyes, & Rodgers, 2016). Concept mapping as a teaching strategy is often implemented in educational setting by teachers for improving the quality of learning (Budd, 2004; Radix & Abdool, 2013; Wheeldon, 2011; Wickramasinghe, Widanapathirana, Kuruppu, Liyanage, & Karunathilake, 2011; Willis & Miertschin, 2006; Zipp, Maher, & D'Antoni, 2011).

Concept mapping helps students in visualizing the main concept instead of focusing on highlighted words or phrases (Gul&Boman, 2006). These concepts are linked through arrow or dotted lines showing the schemata of entire concepts following proper hierarchy (Canas, Hill, Carff, Suri, Lott, Eskridge, Carvajal, 2004).

Concept mapping is a new emerging teaching strategy, mostly employed at secondary levels. In Pakistan, several researchers are made in the field of Science and English, aiming exploration of multidimensional paradigms of teaching and its impact in the form of students' mastery over the subject matter and strong conceptual understanding (Cheema & Mirza, 2013; Rehman&Ambreen, 2018). The main purposes of concept mapping are to construct the knowledge of students, enhance their learning, evaluate the performance of students, focus on ipsative assessment (pre and post assessment of student's progress in academics), checking student understanding level, degree of usability of gained knowledge, and integration of theory in to practice (Safdar et al, 2012).

1.1. Problematic & Predictive Approach

The current study aims to explore the role of concept mapping and the performance of students in their academics at the undergraduate level. The student often dwells on crammed learning, which does not develop critical thinking abilities, thus compromising the main aim of learning. In addition, students take less interest and have lower motivation towards their learning, which affects their academic performance. Due to vague academic concepts, students face tremendous issues in streamlining their concepts in provided educational settings thus resulting in the waste of available resources. The current study therefore sought to explore the usability of concept mapping by teachers as teaching strategy aiming to enhance students' academic repertoire.

1.2. Objectives of Study

The objectives of the study were to:

- a) Explore the role of concept mapping in students' academic development.
- b) Analyze the sequence of concept mapping in terms of instructional taxonomy of learning

1.3. Research Hypotheses

- i) H_0 = Concept mapping does not strengthen student understanding at tertiary level.
 H_1 = Concept mapping strengthens student understanding at tertiary level.
- ii) H_0 = Concept mapping does not enhance academic adjustment of students in a classroom environment.
 H_1 = Concept mapping enhances academic adjustment of students in a classroom environment.
- iii) H_0 = Concept mapping does not help in the development of student cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills.
 H_1 = Concept mapping helps in the development of student cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills.

1.4. Significance of the Study & Appropriate Reasoning

The study is expected to be beneficial for teachers for enhancing their concept mapping skills and will aid students in helping them understand the subject matter in a better way. The study focuses on the application of concept mapping in classroom setting at undergraduate level, which is considered as a healthy activity for teachers as well as students in enriching their skills and practice. This strategy will also help both teachers and students to focus on developing critical thinking abilities and would motivate students towards their academics.

1.5. Focus of the Study

The study was focused to undergraduate level students of the Departments of International Relations, Education and Psychology at National University of Modern Languages, Islamabad.

Literature Review

Teachers often use concept mapping in order to enhance the academic understanding of students and to get desired outcomes in assessment (Abi-El-Mona & Adb-El-Khalick, 2008; Adodo, 2013; Balim, 2013; Chiou, 2008; Holland, Holland, & Davies, 2004; Mahasneh, 2017; Martínez, Pérez, Suero, & Pardo, 2013; Nedungadi, Haridas, & Raman, 2015; Tanriseven, 2014; Youssef & Mansour, 2012). Concept mapping is also applied for enhancing critical thinking skills of students (Chen, Liang, Lee, & Liao, 2011; Kaddoura, Van-Dyke, & Yang, 2016) and is equally helpful in retaining the knowledge of students (Dhindsa & Anderson, 2011; Hu & Wu, 2012; Hwang, Kuo, Chen, & Ho, 2014; Ismail, Ngah, & Umar, 2010). Concept mapping being an important and diverse policy and practice field has been explored from several dimensions. In a study, Balim (2013) conducted research on exploring the effects of using concept-mapping strategy by students in retaining the knowledge and academic performance. Results revealed that students who used concept mapping in their academics gained higher grades and thus performed well in their academics.

Similarly, Chen, Liang, and Liao (2011), conducted a quasi-experimental research study on students to explore the impact of concept mapping and lecture method on the development of critical thinking. Their results revealed that the students in experimental group who were taught the course through concept mapping performed better than the control group. Subsequently, Kaddoura, Van-Dyke and Yang (2016) also conducted an experimental research to explore the impact of concept mapping in developing critical thinking abilities among nursing students. The results revealed that those students who were placed in the group taught through concept mapping had higher cognitive scores than that of the control group. The study recommended the inclusion of concept mapping as a teaching strategy for developing desired skills amongst students regarding their cognitive domain.

According to Hu and Wu (2012), the integration of academic content through concept mapping helps students in developing their cognitive abilities. These findings have also been supported by Gerchak, Besterfield-Sacre, Shuman, & Wolfe (2003). The authors argue that concept mapping can be used as a suitable instrument for assessment of academic performance of students in terms of their level of cognition. Accordingly, Youssef and Mansour (2012) also conducted a quasi-experimental research aiming to know the impact of concept mapping on learning of students. The results indicated that the students feel comfortable when taught through concept mapping and yield better outcomes. Besides these, the research conducted by Chiou (2008) also support the results of Youssef and Mansour (2012) that students perform better in their academics when taught through concept mapping. Concept mapping, for instance, builds the potentialities of students in enriching their academic as well as motivation. For creating academic rigor among students, the teachers are motivated towards the usability of concept mapping as the effective teaching strategy.

According to Chiou (2008), Mahasneh (2017), and Chen, Liang, and Liao (2011) concept mapping helps the students to perform well in their academics. This may be due to developing confidence among students and bringing clarity in their academic concepts. Another study was conducted by Adodo (2013) in which the students were encouraged to engage in self-learning. The results show that students improve their learning through concept mapping along with developing creativity and critical thinking. A study was conducted by Tanriseven (2014) in which the author found that pre-service teachers performed well in given tests while developing planning for tasks. The pre-service teachers were of the notion that concept mapping helps in planning the academic activities and have positive impact on execution of tasks. Mahasneh (2017) conducted a quasi-experimental study on the performance level of students using concept mapping and traditional classroom instruction as teaching strategy. The results revealed that the students' who used concept mapping strategy in their academics performed better than the students' who used traditional classroom instruction. According to Dhindsa and Anderson (2011), the students' performance in terms of quality of education, cognition level, structural knowledge is well grounded and better than students following traditional method of teaching.

According to Schaal (2010) concept mapping is a strategy in which the knowledge is amplified basic instructional taxonomies i.e. cognitive domain, affective domain, and psychomotor domain. Using the concept mapping, critical thinking skills are developed among students, which is the crux of cognitive domain. On the other hand, the students become able to integrate the theory into practice, which is the main theme of affective domain; similarly, the motivation level of students towards their academics is the core of psychomotor domain. Thus, the usability of concept mapping promotes the components of instructional taxonomy and eventually enhance the academics of students. In fact, concept mapping helps in clarifying the confusing and ambiguous academic concepts of students and enable them to make the linkage of these terminologies with other academic concepts (Moreira, 2011).

According to Rueda et al. (2009) concept mapping is often anticipated to enhance the learning of students at all levels. This teaching strategy was employed by Kostovich, Poradzisz, Wood, and O'Brien, (2007) on 120 nursing students to check the learning level. The results revealed that when teachers implement concept mapping in their teaching, it enriches the understanding of students.

According to Novak and Canas (2007), employing the strategy of concept mapping provides new insights into learning, resulting in equipping students to think and act differently, promoting the stances of learning among students along with developing motivational and interest-oriented approach. In addition to that, the sense of developing links between various concepts among students structure their knowledge and understanding the content without any difficulty (Hsu & Chang, 2009). Moreover, concept mapping is used for learning complex concepts using various forms i.e. hierarchical pattern, graphical representation, and circular or triangulated style (Åhlberg&Ahoranta, 2004).

Concept mapping is a medium to link the previous knowledge with the new one. According to Safdar et al (2012), the teacher knows about the usability of concept mapping and is able to prepare the lesson plans; they will be in a better position to communicate their thoughts and are able to build stances among students towards their academics. In a meta-analysis, it was suggested that the knowledge of students could be increased and enhanced by considering the concept mapping in their academics and more often used in retention of complex concepts (Nesbit &Adesope, 2006). The students learn more easily and conformably when the lesson is completed and then the teacher develops concept mapping, because at that very time the students can understand the entire academic concept skillfully. In addition to that, concept mapping is also used by teachers to check the intensity of conceptual clarity of students regarding any topic, content or subject (Hay, 2007).

Methodology

3.1. Research Design

Using a quantitative research design, the study aimed at collecting in-depth information and data from the respondents regarding the study focus.

3.2. Population and Sample

The population of the study constituted all the undergraduate level students of the Department of International Relations (26), Department of Education (47), and Department of Psychology (73) at National University of Modern Languages, Islamabad. The total number of students in these departments at undergraduate level in the session 2017–18 was 146. The sample size of 108 students was selected from the population through proportionate sampling techniques using standardized sample determination techniques (Krijice& Morgan, 1970).

3.3 Research instrument

A closed questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale was developed in the light of literature review and research objectives. Three main themes were developed with the help of literature review i.e. cognitive domain, affective domain, and psychomotor domain. The items included in the cognitive domain were 13, while the affective domain and psychomotor domain were having six items each.

3.3.1 Validity

The questionnaire was validated through face, content, construct validity, and Q – sorting techniques. In case of face validity, the questionnaire was evaluated by three experts, having relevant expertise from the field, while content validity was ensured via literature review. In Q–sorting, the questionnaire was checked through confirmatory approach, in which the categories were already made, and the experts were required to label the construct in each given category. As Q–sorting is almost done at the initial stages of research, at advanced levels, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was made to validate the instrument. The AVE for the questionnaire was 0.87 whereas the composite reliability was 0.965, which means that the validity of both the construct and individual variable are high (Fornell& Larker, 1981; Hair, et al.,1998).

3.3.2 Pilot study and reliability of the study

A concurrent design was used to conduct pilot study, whereas the sample for the pilot study was selected through rule of thumb (Thabane et al., 2010). To collect the data for the pilot study, 15 students were selected, who were not included in the original study. The reliability of the study was checked through Cronbach Alpha having 0.809 (range is 0.4 – 0.9) with 25 numbers of items (Tavakol, & Dennick, 2011).

3.3. Data Collection

Total design was adopted to collect the data from the respondents. The researchers collected the empirical data from the selected sample of the study in each timeframe using closed questionnaire with a five-point Likert scale.

Results

The data gathered from the field was analyzed by applying Friedman test using SPSS v.20. The reason for opting Friedman test was that the nature of variables was dependent, scale of measurement was ordinal, and the

number of samples was more than two. This section presents analysis of three main themes of instructional taxonomies i.e. cognitive domain, affective domain, and psychomotor domain.

Table 1
Theme A: Cognitive domain

Ranks	
Statement	Mean Rank
Concept mapping enhances students' creativity.	7.99
Concept mapping assists to understand the key concepts of the subject.	7.81
Concept mapping supports to improve learning of the course content.	7.74
Concept mapping assists in evaluation of the course content.	7.14
Concept mapping assists in grasping the meaning of course content.	7.11
Concept mapping suggests formulating new effective patterns of learning.	7.07
Concept mapping supports application of theories in practical situations.	7.02
Concept mapping helps to communicate learning to others in the class.	6.75
Concept mapping stimulates independent thinking.	6.73
Concept mapping assists to recall wide range of materials in an appropriate way.	6.63
Concept mapping increases the involvement of student in the class.	6.62
Concept mapping supports in the analysis of relationships between different segments of the topic.	6.38
Concept mapping assists to find gaps in learning of the course content.	6.01

Table 1 above presents statements and their corresponding mean ranks of the data pertaining to cognitive domain. As can be seen from the Table the highest mean rank is 7.99 for the statement "Concept mapping enhances students' creativity," while the lowest mean rank is 6.01 for the statement "Concept mapping assists to find gaps in learning of the course content".

Test Statistics			
N			108
Chi-Square			37.982
Df			12
Asymp. Sig.			.000
	Sig.		.000
		Lower Bound	.000
Monte Carlo Sig.	95% Confidence Interval		
		Upper Bound	.027

The test statistics rejects the null hypothesis "Concept mapping does not strengthen student understanding at tertiary level" with df and p value i.e. $\chi^2(12) = 37.98, p = 0.000 \sim 0.001$.

Table 2
Theme B: Affective domain

Ranks	
Statement	Mean Rank
Concept mapping is a helpful learning strategy.	3.81
Concept mapping is an effective way to receive the lecture attentively.	3.74
Concept mapping encourages to participate in class discussion.	3.55

Concept mapping is concerned with the appreciation of a good improvement in learning.	3.50
Concept mapping is useful to judge the strengths and weakness of the topic.	3.21
Concept mapping demonstrates cooperation in group activities.	3.19

The table 2 reveals the highest mean rank for the statement “Concept mapping is a helpful learning strategy” which was 3.81 while the lowest mean rank for the statement “Concept mapping demonstrates cooperation in group activities” was 3.19.

Test Statistics			
N			108
Chi-Square			15.528
Df			5
Asymp. Sig.			.008
	Sig.		.000
		Lower Bound	.000
Monte Carlo Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	Upper Bound	.027

The test statistics rejects the null hypothesis “Concept mapping does not enhance academic adjustment of students in a classroom environment” with df, and p value i.e. $\chi^2(5) = 15.53, p = 0.000\sim 0.001$.

Table 3
Theme C: Psychomotor domain

Ranks	
Statement	Mean Rank
Concept mapping is concerned with the use of sense organs to obtain the guidance.	3.32
Concept mapping shows readiness to take a particular type of action.	3.19
Concept mapping is a good way to guide in learning a skill.	3.76
Concept mapping is useful in performing learned responses which becomes habitual.	3.49
Concept mapping increased the expertise level of the learner.	3.54
Concept mapping helps in adapting skills to meet problematic situation.	3.69

The table 3 shows the highest mean rank for the statement “Concept mapping is a good way to guide in learning a skill” which was 3.76 while the lowest mean rank was 3.19 for the statement “Concept mapping shows readiness to take a particular type of action”.

Test Statistics			
N			108
Chi-Square			9.954
Df			5
Asymp. Sig.			.077
	Sig.		.093
		Lower Bound	.038
Monte Carlo Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	Upper Bound	.147

The test statistics rejects the null hypothesis “Concept mapping does not help in the development of student cognitive, affective, and psychomotor skills” with df, and p value i.e. $\chi^2(5) = 9.95, p = 0.000\sim 0.001$.

Discussion

Teachers usually use a variety of teaching strategies during their classroom teaching, for ensuring that students have understood the concepts and learning has taken place. Concept mapping is considered as an effective strategy for achieving the goals of learning (Novik&Gowin, 1984). Ausubel theory suggests that concept mapping is used to develop the learning and knowledge retention of students (Ausubel, 1963). Concept mapping at tertiary level enhances learning of students (Wang et al, 2018). Concept mapping is often used to clarify any academic misconceptions and confusion and focus on linking the basic concepts in a certain hierarchical mode. The students mostly develop linkage of various academic terminologies and restructure their knowledge. In fact,

concept mapping is an effective mode of assessing students' misconceptions, knowledge, and stance towards their academics (Watson et al, 2014). In addition, Safdaret al. (2012) stated that the preparation and development of subject matter taught through concept mapping enhances the communication skills of students resulting in development of critical thinking potentialities.

In concept mapping, students are actively engaged in learning. According to theory of constructivism, students gain new knowledge based on previous knowledge and link with the modern trends in learning. This approach helps the students in focusing on conceptual learning that enhance the learning aptitude of students. When the student has clear conceptual understanding in their academics through concept mapping, the role of teachers become an academic facilitator (Govt. of Pakistan, 2006).

The study finds that at tertiary level the concept mapping deems to be considered as a suitable mode of teaching, which subsequently promote the application of concept mapping to get mastery of the subject matter. In addition to that students at tertiary level shows positive attitude to concept mapping because of getting acquaintance to difficult academic concepts and aided in development of linking with the complex terminologies. The students conceptual understanding improved when taught through concept mapping and later it was observed that the students were motivated for learning. Though, initially the students taught through concept mapping faced adjustment problems (Harrison & Gibbons, 2013) which was then attuned by realizing its effectiveness.

Conclusion

The research of Hu and Wu (2012) indicated that students' understanding, and learning can be enhanced through concept mapping as a teaching strategy. These findings support the research of Gerchak, Besterfield-Sacre, Shuman, and Wolfe (2003) that concept mapping is considered as main instrument of assessing the students' academic performance in their field of interest. Besides these, some researchers found that the integration of concept mapping in learning process makes it difficult for students to develop cognitive abilities (Hwang et al., 2014). However, the study concluded that students seem comfortable with concept mapping as a teaching method at tertiary level because of performing well in their academics. It was also observed that the critical thinking of students was high and with high rate of resolving the practical problems faced to them during their teaching learning trajectory. A study conducted by Fahim and Rahimi (2011) stated that the concept mapping enhances the academic performance of students and was also supported by Cheema and Mirza (2013). The research indicate that the concept mapping is useful teaching method as it promotes individual thinking among students and favor conceptual understanding.

Findings & Recommendations

The study recommends & find out that:

- a) The teacher may be involved in formal training to teach through concept mapping for yielding better results at all levels. The teachers may also be motivated so that they may work with dedication.
- b) The concept mapping may be included in the curriculum and topics with high complexity level may be taught through this method because of proven track record of producing desired results.
- c) Students may be guided by teacher about the preparation of concept mapping of lessons. This approach might develop the cognitive skills of students and be in a better position to perform well in their academics.
- d) The traditional teaching method may also be employed as per need because the students may not feel boredom by using single teaching method.

References

- Abi-El-Mona, I., & Adb-El-Khalick, F. (2008). The Influence of Mind Mapping on Eighth graders' Science Achievement. *School Science and mathematics*, 108(7), 298-312.
- Adey, P., & Shayer, M. (1994). *Really raising standards*. London: Routledge.
- Adodo, S. O. (2013). Effect of Mind-Mapping as a Self-Regulated Learning Strategy on Students' Achievement in Basic Science and technology. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(6), 163-172. doi:10.5901/mjss.2013.v4n6p163
- Åhlberg, M., & Ahoranta, V. (2004). What Do Concept Maps Reveal about Pupil's Learning and Thinking. *Annual conference of National Association for Research in Science Teaching*, Vancouver, Canada.
- Ausubel, D. P. (1963). *The psychology of meaningful verbal learning. A Cognitive View*. New York, NY: Holt Rinehart and Winston.
- Balim, A. G. (2013). The Effect of Mind-Mapping Applications on Upper Primary Students Success and Inquiry-Learning Skills in Science and Environment Education. *International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education*, 22(4), 337-352. doi:10.1080/10382046.2013.826543
- Baron, R. A. & Byrne, D. (2003). *Social Psychology*. New Jersey: Pearson Education Inc.
- Ben Salem, S., Cheniti Belcadhi, L., & Braham, R. (2013). Using Concept Maps in Knowledge Assessment of Short and Open Answer Questions. *System Theory, Control and Computing (ICSTCC)*, 2013 17th International Conference.

- Budd, J. W. (2004). Mind Maps as Classroom Exercises. *The Journal of Economic Education*, 35(1), 35-46.
- Cañas, A. J., Hill, J., Carff, R., Suri, N., Lott, J., Eskridge, T. and Carvajal, R. (2004). "CmapTools: A knowledge modeling and sharing environment". In *Concept Maps: Theory, methodology, technology. Proceedings of the first International Conference on Concept Mapping*, Edited by: Cañas, A. J., Novak, J. D. and Gonzalez, F. M. 125–133. Pamplona, Spain: Universidad Publica de Navarra.
- Cañas, A. J., Novak, J. D., & Reiska, P. (2012). Freedom vs. restriction of content and structure during concept mapping—possibilities and limitations for construction and assessment. In A. J. Cañas, J. D. [accessed Jun 13 2018].
- Cañas, A. J., Valerio, A., Lalinde-Pulido, J., Carvalho, M., & Arguedas, M. (2003) Using WordNet for Word Sense Disambiguation to Support Concept Map Construction. Vol. 2857. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science* (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics) (pp. 350-359).
- Cheema, A.B., Mirza, M.S, (2013), Effect of Concept mapping on Students' academic achievement, *Journal of Research and Reflection in Education*, 7(2), 125 – 132
- Chen, S. L., Liang, T., Lee, M. L., & Liao, I. C. (2011). Effects of Concept Map Teaching on Students' Critical Thinking and Approach to Learning and Studying. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 50(8), 466-469. doi:10.3928/01484834-20110415-06
- Chen, S.-M., & Bai, S.-M. (2010). Using Data Mining Techniques to Automatically Construct Concept Maps for Adaptive Learning Systems. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 37(6), 4496-4503.
- Chen, S.-M., & Sue, P.-J. (2013). Constructing Concept Maps for Adaptive Learning Systems based on Data Mining Techniques. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 40(7), 2746-2755.
- Chiou, C.-C. (2008). The Effect of Concept Mapping on Students' Learning Achievements and Interests. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 45(4), 375-387.
- Coffey, J. W., Reichherzer, T., Owsnick-Klewe, B., & Wilde, N. (2012). Automated Concept Map Generation from Service-Oriented Architecture Artifacts. In A. J. Cañas, J. D. Novak & J. Vanhear (Eds.), *Concept Maps: Theory, Methodology, Technology*. Proc. of the Fifth Int. Conference on Concept Mapping. Valletta, Malta: University of Malta.
- Dhindsa, H. S., & Anderson, O. R. (2011). Constructivist-Visual Mind Map Teaching Approach and the Quality of Students' Cognitive Structures. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 20(2), 186-200.
- Fahim, M., & Rahimi, A. H. (2011). The effect of concept mapping strategy on the writing performance of EFL learners. *Journal of Academic and Applied Studies*, 1(5), 1-8.
- Fornell and Larcker (1981) Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error. *Journal of Marketing*.
- Gerchak, J., Besterfield-Sacre, M., Shuman, L. J., & Wolfe, H. (2003). Using Concept Maps for Evaluating Program Objectives. In *Proceedings of the Frontiers in Education Conference*.
- Govt. of Pakistan. (2006). National curriculum for General Science, grade IV- VIII. Islamabad; Ministry of Education.
- Gul, R. and Boman, J. (2006) 'Concept Mapping: A strategy for teaching and evaluation in nursing education', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 6(4), 199-206.
- Hair, J.F. Jr., Anderson, R.E., Tatham, R.L., & Black W. C. (1998). *Multivariate Data Analysis (5th ed.)*. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Prentice
- Harrison S, Gibbons C. (2013). Nursing student perceptions of concept maps: from theory to practice. *NursEducPerspect*. 34(6), 395-9.
- Hay, D. B. (2007). Using concept maps to measure deep, surface and non-learning outcomes. *Studies in Higher Education*, 32(1), 39–57.
- Hay, D. B., Kinchin, I. M., & Lygo-Baker, S. (2008). Making learning visible: The role of concept mapping in higher education. *Studies in Higher Education*, 33, 295–311.
- Henige, K. (2012). Use of concept mapping in an undergraduate introductory exercise physiology course. *Advances in Physiology Education*, 36, 197–206
- Hilbert, T. S. & Renkl, A. (2007). *Concept mapping as a follow up strategy to teaching from texts: what characterizes good and poor mappers? Instructional Science*, Springer Neither Land.
- Holland, B., Holland, L., & Davies, J. (2004). *An Investigation into the Concept of Mind Mapping and the Use of Mind Mapping Software to Support and Improve Student Academic Performance*: University of Wolverhampton.
- Hsu, C. M., & Chang, I. H. (2009). The Relationship between Computer-Based Concept Mapping and Creative Performance. *Asian Journal of Arts and Sciences*, (86), 16– 36.
- Hu, M. L. M., & Wu, M. H. (2012). The Effect of Concept Mapping on Students' Cognitive Load. *World Transactions on Engineering and Technology Education*, 10(2), 134-137.
- Huffman, K. (2004). *Psychology in Action*. John Wiley and Sons, Inc.

- Hwang, G. J., Kuo, F. R., Chen, N. S., & Ho, H. J. (2014). Effects of an Integrated Concept Mapping and Webbased Problem-Solving Approach on Students' Learning Achievements, Perceptions and Cognitive Loads. *Computers and Education*, 71, 77-86. doi:10.1016/j.compedu.2013.09.013
- Iqbal, H.M. (2011). *Education in Pakistan: Developmental milestones*. Lahore: Paramount Publishing Enterprise.
- Ismail, M. N., Ngah, N. A., & Umar, I. N. (2010). The Effects of Mind Mapping with Cooperative Learning on Programming Performance, Problem Solving Skill and Metacognitive Knowledge among Computer Science Students. *Journal of Educational Computing Research*, 42(1), 35-61. doi:10.2190/EC.42.1.b
- Jetter, A. J., & Kok, K. (2014). Fuzzy Cognitive Maps for Futures Studies-A Methodological Assessment of Concepts and Methods. *Futures*.
- Joyce, B., Weil, M., & Calhoun, E. (2004). *Models of teaching*. Pearson Education Inc.
- Kaddoura, M., Van-Dyke, O., & Yang, Q. (2016). Impact of a Concept Map Teaching Approach on Nursing Students' Critical Thinking Skills. *Nursing & Health sciences*, 18(3), 350-354. doi:10.1111/nhs.12277
- Ke, Z. (2013). Research on the Approach of Automatic Construct Concept Maps from Online Course. *Information Technology Journal*, 12(24), 8020-8024. doi:10.3923/itj.2013.8020.8024
- Kibar, Z. B., Yaman, F., & Ayas, A. (2013). Assessing Prospective Chemistry Teachers' Understanding of Gas through Qualitative and Quantitative Analyses of their Concept Maps. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 14(4), 542-554.
- Kostovich, C. T., Poradzisz, M., Wood, K., & O'Brien, K. L. (2007). Learning style preference and student aptitude for concept maps. *Journal of Nursing Education*, 46(5), 217-224.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Kumaran, V. S., & Sankar, A. (2013). An Automated Assessment of Students' Learning in e-Learning Using Concept Map and Ontology Mapping Advances in Web-Based Learning. In *ICWL 2013* (pp. 274-283): Springer.
- Lukša, Ž. (2011). Učeničkorazumijevanje i usvojenost osnovnih koncepta u biologiji: doktorska disertacija. Zagreb, Sveučilište u Zagrebu, PMF - Biološki odsjek
- Mahasneh, A. M. (2017). The Effect of Using Electronic Mind Mapping on achievement and attitudes in an introduction to educational psychology course. *New Educational Review*, 47(1), 295-304. doi:10.15804/ner.2017.47.1.23
- Martínez, G., Pérez, Á. L., Suero, M. I., & Pardo, P. J. (2013). The Effectiveness of Concept Maps in Teaching Physics Concepts Applied to Engineering Education: Experimental Comparison of the Amount of Learning Achieved with and without Concept Maps. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 22(2), 204-214. doi:10.1007/s10956-012-9386-8
- Mintzes, J., Wandersee, J. and Novak, J. (2000) *Assessing Science Understanding*. San Diego: Academic Press
- Moreira, M. A. (2011). Why concepts, why meaningful learning, why collaborative activities and why concept maps? *Aprendizagem Significativa em Revista / Meaningful Learning Review*, 1(3), 1-11.
- Nedungadi, P., Haridas, M., & Raman, R. (2015). Blending Concept Maps with Online labs (OLabs): Case study with Biological Science. In *ACM International Conference Proceeding Series*.
- Nesbit, J. C. & Adesope, O. O. (2006). Learning with concept and knowledge maps: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research*, 76(3), 413-448.
- Novak, J. D. & Cañas A. J. (2006a). The origins of concept mapping tool and the continuing evolution of the tool. *Information Visualization*, 5, 175-184.
- Novak, J. D., & Gowin, D. B. (1984). *Learning how to learn*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Novak, J. D., & Cañas, A. J. (2007). Theoretical origins of concept maps, how to construct them, and uses in education. *Reflecting Education*, 3(1), 29-42.
- O'Donnell, A.M., Dansereau, D.F. & Hall, R.H. (2002). Knowledge maps as scaffolds for cognitive processing. *Educational Psychology Review*, 14(1), 71-86.
- Qasim, I., Jeong, J. W., Heu, J. U., & Lee, D. H. (2013). Concept map Construction from Text Documents using Affinity Propagation. *Journal of Information Science*, 39(6), 719-736. doi:10.1177/0165551513494645
- Radix, C.-A., & Abdool, A. (2013). Using Mind Maps for the Measurement and Improvement of Learning Quality. *The Caribbean Teaching Scholar*, 3(1).
- Rehman, R., Abreen, M., (2018), Concept mapping for improving expository writing in second language, *Pakistan Journal of Education*, 35(2), 17-36
- Rueda, U., Arruarte, A., Elorriaga, J. A., & Herran, E. (2009). Learning the attachment theory with the CM-ED concept map editor. *Computers & Education*, 52(2), 460-469.
- Safdar, M., Hussain, A., Shah, I., Rifat, Q., (2012), Concept Maps: An instructional tool to facilitate meaningful learning, *European Journal of Educational Research*, 1(1), 55 - 64

- Schaal, S. (2010). Enriching traditional biology lectures digital concept maps and their influence on cognition and motivation. *World Journal on Educational Technology*, 2(1), 42–54.
- Tanriseven, I. (2014). A Tool that can be Effective in the Self-Regulated Learning of Pre-Service teachers: The Mind Map. *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, 39(1). doi:10.14221/ajte.2014v39n1.1
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International journal of medical education*, 2, 53.
- Thabaneet al.(2010)BMC Medical Research Methodology, 10:1 <http://www.biomedcentral.com/1471-2288/10/1>
- Valerio Arbizu, A. (2014). Extracting Knowledge from Documents to Construct Concept Maps. Indiana University.
- Wang, M.; Wu, B.; Kirschner, P.A.; Spector, J.M. (2018), Using cognitive mapping to foster deeper learning with complex problems in a computer-based environment. *Comput. Hum. Behav.* 87, 450–458.
- Watson, M. K., Pelkey, J., Noyes, C. R., & Rodgers, M. O. (2016). Assessing Conceptual Knowledge Using Three Concept Map Scoring Methods. *Journal of Engineering Education*, 105(1), 118-146. doi:10.1002/jee.20111
- Watson, M.K.; Pelkey, J.; Noyes, C.R.; Rodgers, M.O. (2014). Use of Concept Maps to Assess Student Sustainability Knowledge. In Proceedings of the American Society for Engineering Education Annual Conference and Exposition, Indianapolis, IN, USA, 15–18.
- Wheeldon, J. (2011). Is a Picture Worth a Thousand Words? Using Mind Maps to Facilitate Participant Recall in Qualitative Research. *The Qualitative Report*, 16(2), 509.
- Wickramasinghe, A., Widanapathirana, N., Kuruppu, O., Liyanage, I., & Karunathilake, I. (2011). Effectiveness of Mind Maps as a Learning Tool for Medical Students. *South East Asian Journal of Medical Education*.
- Willis, C. L., & Miertschin, S. L. (2006). Mind Maps as Active Learning Tools. *Journal of Computing Sciences in Colleges*, 21(4), 266-272.
- Youssef, H. A. M., & Mansour, M. A. M. (2012). The Effect of Concept Mapping on Students' Learning Achievements and Interests in Taif University. *Life Science Journal*, 9(SUPPL.2), 346-353.
- Zipp, G. P., Maher, C., & D'Antoni, A. V. (2011). Mind Maps: Useful Schematic Tool for Organizing and Integrating Concepts of Complex Patient Care in the Clinic and Classroom. *Journal of College Teaching & Learning (TLC)*, 6(2); 59 – 68

Author Information

Dr. Obaid Ullah

Lecturer & Coordinator, Department of Education,
National University of Modern Languages,
Islamabad

Dr. Saira Nudrat

Assistant Professor, Department of Education,
National University of Modern Languages,
Islamabad

Prof. Dr. Abdul Waheed Mughal

Dean, Faculty of Arts, Social Sciences and
Education, Sarhad University of Science & IT,
Peshawar
